

This is the galactical multi-verse model, of the list of types of people and creatures, contained by the vapour dream cosmos, which goes as followed:

- The monkey-verse, the monk-ey people and monk-ey creatures and monk-ey plants.
- The golem-verse, the golem people and golem creatures and golem plants.
- The cartoon-verse, the cartoon people and cartoon creatures and cartoon plants.
- The vampire-verse, the vampire people and vampire creatures and vampire plants.
- The toy-verse, the toy people and toy creatures and toy plants.
- The gremlin-verse, the gremlin people and gremlin creatures and gremlin plants.
- The hobbit-verse, the hobbit people and hobbit creatures and hobbit plants.
- The nerd-verse, the nerd people and nerd creatures and nerd plants.
- The muso-verse, the muso people and muso creatures and muso plants.
- The fairy-verse, the fairy people and fairy creatures and fairy plants.
- The plant-verse, the plant people and plant creatures and plant plants.
- The mushroom-verse, the mushroom people and mushroom creatures and mushroom plants.
- The wolven-verse, the wolven people and wolven creatures and wolven plants.
- The cat-verse, the cat people and cat creatures and cat plants.
- The grown-up-verse, the grown-up people and grown-up creatures and grown-up plants.
- The ogre-verse, the ogre people and ogre creatures and ogre plants.
- The actor-verse, the actor people and actor creatures and actor plants.
- The robot-verse, the robot people and robot creatures and robot plants.
- The pirate-verse, the pirate people and pirate creatures and pirate plants.
- The toddler-verse, the toddler people and toddler creatures and toddler plants.
- The alien-verse, the alien people and alien creatures and alien plants.
- The theatre-verse, the theatrical people and theatrical creatures and theatrical plants.
- The android-verse, the android people and android creatures and android plants.
- The political-verse, the political people and political creatures and political plants.
- The professor-verse, the professor people and professor creatures and professor plants.
- The hair-verse, the media people and media creatures and media plants.
- The warrior-verse, the warrior people and warrior creatures and warrior plants.
- The doctor-verse, the doctor people and doctor creatures and doctor plants.
- The hero-verse, the hero people and hero creatures and hero plants.
- The rodent-verse, the rodent people and rodent creatures and rodent plants.
- The tea-verse, the tea people and the tea creatures and tea plants.
- The law-verse, the law people and the law creatures and law plants.
- The human-verse, the human people and human creatures and human plants.
- The muppet-verse, the muppet people and the muppet creatures and the muppet plants.

And as well the extra:

- The dream-verse, the 2D + 2 ExtraD image people and the 2D + 2 ExtraD image creatures and the 2D + 2 ExtraD image plants twinned with the 2D + 2 ExtraD characters and the 2D + 2 ExtraD character aspects and the 2D + 2 ExtraD character plants.

When sunset, then this model is set, of a setless set.